

A MARKETING APPROACH OF MOROCCAN POLITICIANS' USES ON SOCIAL NETWORKS SITES

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ABSTRACT: The attendance of Moroccan politicians on the Social Networks Sites (SNS) is an undeniable reality. However, the questions of how Moroccan politicians use these new communication and mobilization devices, and to what extent they take advantage of the huge potentialities they offer, remain unanswered. The content analysis of a 160 posts made by a sample of 16 active Moroccan politicians on *Facebook* shows that they don't use all the proposed features. Results indicate nevertheless slight differences in use between incumbents and challengers.

KEY WORDS: Social Networks Sites; Moroccan politicians; Uses

RESUME : La présence des Hommes politiques marocains sur les sites de réseaux sociaux (SRS) est une réalité indéniable. L'analyse de contenu de 160 publications d'un échantillon de 16 Hommes politiques marocains actifs sur *Facebook* montre qu'ils n'utilisent pas toutes les fonctionnalités proposées. Les résultats indiquent néanmoins de légères différences d'usages entre les Hommes politiques au pouvoir et ceux à l'opposition.

Mots clés : Sites de Réseaux Sociaux, Hommes politiques marocains ; Usages

1. Introduction

The rapid rise of the social networks sites (SNS) and the multiplication of their audience have greatly seduced the politicians (Castells, 2007; Lin, 2017). Some researchers consider even that the professionalization of modern political campaigns has without any doubt rendered digital media a tool which politicians cannot avoid and which they need to master (Maarek, 2014). The phenomenon began in the USA in the 2008 elections before spreading around the world (Towner and Dulio, 2012).

In Morocco, a simple navigation on the *Facebook* or *Twitter* sites shows that politicians have registered in this trend. Indeed, a multitude of accounts, pages and groups associated with politicians are easily visible and accessible on these very attractive social networking sites. But, what exactly do politicians do on these new communication platforms? And how much do they benefit from the multiple features they offer? The questions deserve to be asked because the impact of SNS on attitudes and political behavior is constantly being demonstrated (e.g., Towner and Munoz, 2018; Boulianne, 2017; Halpern et al., 2017; Lin, 2017; Kim et al., 2016; Casteltrione, 2015; Dimitrova et al., 2014; Ahmad and Popa, 2014; Gil de Zúñiga et al., 2013; Bode et al., 2013).

Moreover, the literature review developed in the following section shows that politicians have a range of tools on SNS to achieve their goals of communication, persuasion and influence. Several studies have focused on the comparison of potential and real uses of SNS by politicians. But, most of the research work on the uses of SNS in political campaigns has been made in developed countries, especially in USA. In Morocco we have spotted only a few and scattered studies. Knowledge about Moroccan politicians' practices is still at embryonic stage. To address this gap, this research intends to explore this question in the Moroccan field through the content analysis of 160 publications of a sample composed of 16 active Moroccan politicians on *Facebook*.

The article is structured as follows. The second point will be dedicated to the theoretical background. Then, we will develop the research methodology and data collection. In the fourth section, data analysis and findings are presented. In a final section, we will compare the results

A MARKETING APPROACH OF MOROCCAN POLITICIANS' USES ON SOCIAL NETWORKS SITES

obtained from the content analysis of politicians' publications with the lessons drawn from the literature on the potential and actual uses of SNS.

2. Theoretical background

Information and communication technologies have always been instrumentalized for persuasion by politicians. A historical approach to this relationship shows that « *without these media, politicians would find it difficult if not impossible to mobilise their supporters and persuade the undecided voters to support them* » (Stanyer, 2005, p.1050). That is why every time a new communication technology emerges, political actors, whether political parties or politicians, rush to integrate it into their communication and mobilization plan. It started with radio, then television and in recent years it's the internet that attracts more and more politicians, especially since all the other media are converging to it (Coleman, 2001). The presence of politicians on digital social networks is part of this trend that wattal et al. (2010), aptly describe as « *migration of politics from place to space* » (p.670). According de Utz, (2009), « *the huge and increasing number of users makes SNS an interesting venue for marketing and political campaigns* » (p.221). Before collecting the different uses made of SNS by politicians in the literature, it is first of all necessary to define and delimit these new communication technologies. As our field of study, the goal is to distinguish them from a number of applications and devices that have accompanied the advent of so-called web 2.0.

2.1. Defining social networks sites

The question of exactly what a social networks site means is relevant to the extent that other neighboring expressions are also used and are often confused with SNS (Stenger and Coutant, 2010). These include mainly “*web 2.0*”, “*social media*” and “*virtual communities*”. Boyd and Ellison, (2008), proposed a first definition of SNS. SNS are a « *web-based services that allow individuals to (1) construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, (2) articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection, and (3) view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system. The nature and nomenclature of these connections may vary from site to site* » (p. 211). SNS therefore

A MARKETING APPROACH OF MOROCCAN POLITICIANS' USES ON SOCIAL NETWORKS SITES

encompass any web-based applications allowing individuals to connect, communicate, and collaborate with one another. This is usually done through individual user profiles and allows users to share information and join networks based on geographic location or interests (White et al. 2009).

Considering that these definitions are not clear enough as they are based solely on technology, Stenger and Coutant, (2009), enriches it by adding a fourth characteristic. According to the authors, SNS are « *web-based services that allow individuals to: (1) construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, (2) articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection, and (3) view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system. The nature and nomenclature of these connections may vary from site to site. (4) Base their interest mainly on these first three points and not on any particular activity* (p.5). Another more recent definition of SNS is that of Ellison and Boyd, (2013), who consider a SNS as « *a networked communication platform in which participants 1) have uniquely identifiable profiles that consist of user-supplied content, content provided by other users, and/or system-level data; 2) can publicly articulate connections that can be viewed and traversed by others; and 3) can consume, produce, and/or interact with streams of user-generated content provided by their connections on the site* ».

It should be noted that the birth of the SNS is part of the emergence of what is called the web 2.0. In his founding article titled: "What Is Web 2.0? Design Patterns and Business Models for the Next Generation of Software", Tim O'Reilly, (2005), points out that the web 2.0 can be visualized as « *a set of principles and practices that tie together a veritable solar system of sites that demonstrate some or all of those principles, at a varying distance from that core* ». Among these principles, O'Reilly, (2005), cites: user participation in content creation, collective intelligence, data power, service delivery instead of product offering, flexibility in user interfaces and release of the software from the only personal computer (PC). Beyond a technological revolution, some authors describe web 2.0 as an evolution in the uses made of the web. In other terms, it is a cultural and informational evolution. Among the concepts associated with web 2.0 there is "social media".

According to Dictionnaire Cambridge Advanced Learner's & Thesaurus © Cambridge University Press, social media encompasses all websites and computer programs that allow people to communicate and share information on the internet using a computer or mobile phone. In other words, social media is a web-based and mobile-based Internet application that allow the creation, access and exchange of user-generated content that is ubiquitously accessible (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010). So they include a varied ecology of sites which vary in terms of their scope and functionality (Kietzmann et al. 2011). In addition to digital social networks, social media encompasses several other sites and applications such as forums, microblogging, social bookmarking, social curation, RSS and wikis (Batrinca and Treleven, 2015).

Virtual communities are also an expression that is often confused with SNS. Boyd and Ellison, (2008) explain clearly the nuance between the two expressions: « *SNSs are primarily organized around people, not interests. Early public online communities such as Usenet and public discussion forums were structured by topics or according to topical hierarchies, but social network sites are structured as personal (or «egocentric») networks, with the individual at the center of their own community* » (p.219). To situate them in the technological landscape born of the evolution of the Internet, we can say, as shown in figure 1, that social networks sites are part of social media. These are a main component of web 2.0 which is considered a new generation of web on the internet. Moreover, « *Several classifications of SNS have been put forward: professional vs. personal networks, networking vs. navigation networks, expressive vs. collaborative networks etc* » (Erragcha and Romdhane, 2014, p.82). We can also distinguish between generalist sites, such as facebook and specialized sites, such as youtube.

Figure 1: Position of the SNS in the digital landscape

Source: Adaped Erragcha and Romdhane, (2014), p.80

2.2. Uses and Gratifications (U&G) as an approach to SNS

The theory of uses and gratifications is one of the most used theories to understand and explain the use of media (Ruggiero, 2000). It is a theory derived from communication sciences (Whiting and Williams, 2013). It is described by Katz et al. (1974) as « *an attempt to explain a phenomenon by questioning an individual about how he uses communications, instead of other resources in his environment, to meet his needs and achieve his goals* » (p.21). Proponents of this theory emphasize the active role of users in choosing and using a medium. Users select the media and their content according to the needs they are trying to satisfy (LaRose, 2011). These audience members « *use "actively" the media to obtain specific satisfactions that meet psychological or psychosociological needs* » (Proulx, 2005, p.8).

U&G theory has been considered from the start as « *a natural paradigm for understanding internet use* » (LaRose et al. 2001, p.396). The emergence of computer-assisted communication media has rekindled the importance of U&G in research on the uses of mass media (Ruggiero, 2000). In fact, this theoretical framework has always provided, according to Ruggiero, (2000), « *a cutting-edge theoretical approach in the early stages of each new mass communication medium: newspapers, radio and television, and now the Internet* » (p.3).

A MARKETING APPROACH OF MOROCCAN POLITICIANS' USES ON SOCIAL NETWORKS SITES

Based on different arguments, many authors have emphasized the utility of U&G in the study of social media. Whiting and Williams, (2013), for instance, consider that the application of this theory « *helps explain the many and varied reasons for using these new communication media* » (p.367). U&G theory is « *a relevant theoretical approach in the context of online research* » (Dunne et al., 2010, p.46), because it focuses on the active use of media, and is capable of to cover both the mass dimension of communication and the interpersonal dimension (LaRose et al., 2001). It is also an approach that lends itself well to the study of the Internet, because of its interactive nature and the fact that the uses and gratifications are based on the choice made by the audience (Ruggiero, 2000).

Despite the limitations mentioned by some authors such as LaRose, (2004), the U&G approach « *is still a useful framework for understanding the use of the Internet and the needs of its users* » (Park et al. 2009, p.730). One of his strengths is that « *it is easily applicable to a wide variety of situations involving mediated communication* » (Lin, 1996, p.574). As such, it is considered by the author to be one of the most appropriate theoretical frameworks for studying the psychological and behavioral trends in media communication.

The interactivity associated with the new generation of the internet and the directed nature or objective oriented of its users make the U&G approach particularly suitable for examining the use of social media for marketing purposes (Stafford et al., 2004). The U&G approach is also « *one of the ways to explore the needs of individuals to use digital social networks* » (Raacke and Bonds-Raacke, 2008, p.170). Therefore, the theory of U&G deserves, according to Whiting and Williams, (2013), special attention and should be highlighted in studies on social media. For all these reasons, we have chosen the U&G as a reference theory to answer the two questions posed above. Based on the U&G theory, several studies have identified why SNS are used and what benefits are derived from them. Table 1 presents examples of this research work.

Table 1: Examples of SNS' gratifications in the literature

Auteurs	Gratifications	Objet de l'étude
Sheldon, (2008)	Relationship maintenance; Passing time; Virtual community; Entertainment ; Coolness; Companionship	Students users of Facebook
Joinson, (2008)	Social connection; Shared identities; Content; Social investigation; Social network Surfing, Status updating	Facebook users
Boyd and Ellison, (2008)	Self presentation; Networking; Information sharing	Social networks sites
Park et al., (2009)	Socializing; Entertainment; Self-status seeking; Information	Students groups on Facebook
Shen and Khalifa, (2010)	Performance expectancy; Social influences; Effort expectancy; Facilitating conditions	Social networks sites
Cheung et al., (2011)	Purposive value; Self-discovery; Maintaining interpersonal interconnectivity; Social enhancement ; Entertainment	Students users of Facebook
Hunt et al., (2012)	Interpersonal utility; Entertainment; Self-expression	Facebook users
Whiting and Williams, (2013)	Social interaction ; Information seeking ; Pass time; Entertainment; Relaxation ; Communicatory utility; Convenience utility; Expression of opinion; Information sharing; Surveillance/knowledge about others	Consumers users of social media
Park, (2013)	Information seeking; Mobilization; Public expression	Opinion leaders on Twitter
Al-jabri et al., (2015)	Self presentation; Social interaction; Freedom of speech; Enjoyment	Twitter users
Salehan et al., (2017)	Vertical social; Horizontal social; Hedonic motivations; Utilitarian motivations	Users on Cyworld.com, Facebook.com, Twitter.com, and other social networking services.

The table above shows clearly that SNS are used to meet a multitude of needs. The categorization of the different uses of SNS reported in the literature allows us to highlight several types of uses: self presentation, information, relationship, interaction, community, mobilization and social enhancement. However, what about politicians' practices on SNS?

2.3. Political marketing uses on SNS

The presence of politicians on the SNS is part of the sub-discipline of the digital marketing. Simply Chaffery and Ellis-Chadwick, (2012), define this one as « *the achieving marketing objectives through applying digital technologies* » (p.10). It is clear that political campaigning is also increasingly influenced by these new technologies (Utz, 2009). Indeed, the development of interactive and horizontal communication networks such as the SNS has led to the emergence of new forms of communication and “*mass self-communication*” (Castells, 2007). Towner and Dulio, (2012), note at this level that « *The Internet has provided a wealth of opportunities for candidates and their campaigns to use technology in creative and innovative ways* » (p.95). The authors add that the 2008 U.S. presidential campaign clearly illustrated this. Furthermore, « *The emergence and adaptation of online communication technologies, such as Facebook, Twitter and Google Plus, have dramatically changed communication between politicians and their constituents during elections* » (Lin, 2017, p.77). Thanks to SNS, users can access, share and download information, videos, audios, photos, at any given time and from anywhere (Aljabri et al. 2015). They can also communicate, share, and discuss ideas (Raacke and Bonds-Raacke, 2008).

Many researchers deem that SNS have offered politicians multiple features in order to achieve their goals. First, they provided a highly visible environment for candidates to promote themselves, articulate their platforms, and interact with voters in fundamentally different ways (Vitak et al. 2011). SNS like *Facebook* go beyond simply communicating the campaign's theme and providing information. Active engagement by the candidate and a well-maintained presence can make the candidate more accessible and seem more authentic (Williams and Gulati, 2012). The case of Barack Obama's election in 2008 is often cited in the literature as an example of the successful use of SNS in political marketing (Towner and Dulio, 2012, Wattal et al., 2010). Indeed, during its election campaign « *community platforms were used to recruit supporters, mobilize partisans, counter rumors and multiply the audience of traditional media* » (Mercanti-Guérin, 2010, p.17). This performance is mainly due to the fact that SNS have become effective channels for direct messaging to target voters (Kim, Atkin and Lin, 2016). Moreover, SNS « *provide an opportunity to reach individuals less interested in politics. Viewing a candidate's profile further strengthened existing attitudes.* » (Utz, 2009, p.221).

A MARKETING APPROACH OF MOROCCAN POLITICIANS' USES ON SOCIAL NETWORKS SITES

These digital media « *go further by reaching potential voters who have no interest in politics and do not visit political blogs or websites* » (Maarek, 2014, p.19). In fact, SNS offer politicians « *the facility for engaging in two-way communication with members in terms of personalised messages and content* » (Dunne et al., 2010, p.48).

In advance and after of both decision and marketing action, politicians can also use the SNS to access to substantial information about site members and to collect valuable data on the behavior and attitudes of Internet users (Boulianne, 2017; Bille, 2015). Indeed, « *server-level data offer a unique opportunity to access elaborated behavioural data about what people are doing on SNSs* » (Ellison and Boyd, 2013, p.151). Various data mining techniques are now available to collect process and analyze this data (Kavitha, 2017; Adedoyin-Olowe et al. 2013) that are so abundant that we call them *big data*. The major marketing interest of big data is the possibility of micro-targeting that they allow (Newman, 2016). Now, politicians can reach many more people in an individualized way (Shorey and Howard, 2016). Indeed, « *Through elaborate techniques of mapping individuals tastes and distastes, digital media are particularly helpful for reaching swing voters which may change the outcome of an election or help carrying an unpopular but necessary political decision* » (Maarek, 2014, p.20). In addition to the data available on these communication platforms, politicians can conduct surveys or polls which allow them to have more primary data (Bode, 2012).

SNS are also used by politicians to raise funds for their campaigns (Maarek, 2014). Through individual micro contributions, politicians can take advantage of the thousands of fans they have on the SNS. By mobilizing a multi-channel campaign that emphasized social network sites, Barak Obama, for instance, has succeeded to amass a slew of small donations during the elections of 2008 and 2012 (Bimber, 2014). Thanks to the SNS, Donald Trump was also able to raise millions of dollars for his campaign in 2016. The impact of SNS on fundraising could be explained by the fact that several studies have shown that users of these new communication platforms are more connected, more active and more politically engaged (e.g., Lin, 2017; Kim et al., 2016; Casteltrionne, 2015; Boulianne, 2015; Gil de Zuniga, 2014; Laurie et al., 2013; Gustafsson, 2012; Bode, 2012).

It seems therefore that SNS can be used by politicians as tools of marketization and professionalization of their campaigns. Many studies have examined the uses of SNS by

A MARKETING APPROACH OF MOROCCAN POLITICIANS' USES ON SOCIAL NETWORKS SITES

politicians in other countries, especially USA and United Kingdom. But, what about Morocco? Before answering this question, it is important to clarify the methodology used to collect process and analyze data about morrocan politician's practices on *Facebook*, as exemple of SNS. This is the purpose of the following section.

3. Research methodology and data collection

The aim of this study is to obtain a description of how morrocan politicians use SNS, especially facebook. To analyze the content of SNS, several methodologies are possible. Among these methodologies, we find social network analysis (SNA). Mercanti-Guérin, (2010), note that SNA is a newly emerging methodology for the study of on-line communities in marketing and consider that « *it is above all a toolbox for visualizing and modeling social relations as nodes (individuals, organizations ...) and links (relationships between these nodes)* » (p.134). Nevertheless, Stenger and Coutant, (2010), think that the conditions required for the SNA, namely a structure composed of social entities and social relations, complete network and systematic observation, « *are particularly demanding and it is not easy to imagine answering them in the case of the analysis of a SNS for the moment* » (p.223).

The survey is another tool that can provide data on the uses made of the SNS (Utz, 2009). Some authors consider, however, that it is not entirely adapted to the new forms of interaction whose intensity is lower than in the case of offline (Bastien, 2013).

In addition, the questionnaires allow only a declarative material whose risk of error is high, especially as it is not situated in its context (Cefai, 2010). Experimentation can also be used to extract data online (Utz, 2009), but netnographic methods are the most recommended in the literature (Bastien, 2013; Kozinets, 2010; Bowler, 2010; Stenger and Coutant, 2009; Bernard, 2006).

For our case, we observed for six months, from February 1 to July 31, 2018, the facebook pages of a a sample of convenience of 16 Moroccan politicians. The aim was to extract posts of each politician. By the technique of "screenshot" we could build a database of different publications on their facebook pages. Given the rather high volume of posts included in the corpus initially archived during the six months of observation, we limited ourselves to a random sample of 160 posts (10 posts per politician). These images have been processed and

A MARKETING APPROACH OF MOROCCAN POLITICIANS' USES ON SOCIAL NETWORKS SITES

categorized on the basis of an analysis grid composed of the following usage classes: Information, Mobilization, interaction, polling, and fundraising. It should be noted here that this analysis grid is primarily the result of the literature review on the uses of SNS in general, but also draws on some works done in other contexts, such as Small, (2010).

The choice of SNS facebook is explained by its strong penetration in Morocco. Recent statistics suggest that Facebook is the more popular among morrocan internet users. This SNS is also well known for social interaction and information sharing. Several modalities of presence are proposed to the members on *Facebook*: accounts, groups or pages. We did not choose the groups because it is the idea of community which prevails there. We opted in our study for the pages, because at the base, they were created by facebook to allow the personalities and the companies to communicate with their fans or customers. They also allow having statistics on the visitors and thus a global vision of the audience. Communication is essentially unidirectional, but it also offers the opportunity to interact. Another advantage for our case is that the publications of the pages are taken by default in the news feeds of the subscribers. Just like a page to be connected and receive updates in his newsfeed. Furthermore, unlike groups, pages are always public and open. Pages can in fine host applications and therefore offer more content and interaction.

The sample is made up of 16 Moroccan politicians most visible and dynamic on *Facebook*. The pages observed were identified using the search engine on facebook accounts. 10 politicians belong to political parties participating in the government (PJD, RNI, MP and PPS); 6 belong to opposition parties (PAM, PI, FGD). On the sex side, 13 are men and 3 are women. In terms of age, the sample is heterogeneous. The age of participants varies between 30 and 70 years old). We have, by this sample of convenience, made sure that the sample is representative of the Moroccan political class present on facebook.

Regarding the analysis of the data collected, we chose the method of content analysis. According to Bardin, (2007), it's a descriptive qualitative approach to data analysis. The content to be analyzed can be texts, images, words or speeches. The content analysis is based, according to Allard-Poesi et al. (2007), on « *the assumption that the repetition of discourse analysis units (words, expressions or similar meanings, sentences, paragraphs) reveals the centers of interest, the concerns of the authors of the discourse* » p.493. Different phases of

A MARKETING APPROACH OF MOROCCAN POLITICIANS' USES ON SOCIAL NETWORKS SITES

the content analysis are organized around three chronological poles: the pre-analysis, the exploitation of the material, the treatment of the results, the inference and the interpretation (Bardin, 2013).

In political communication, content analysis is « *a means of measuring or quantifying dimensions of the content of messages* » (Benoit, 2011, p. 268). The author adds that « *content analysis can be employed to describe a group of related messages, draw inferences about the sources that produced those messages, or draw inferences about the reception of those messages by their audience* » (p.269). It is therefore an effort of interpretation that sways between two poles, on the one hand, the rigor of objectivity, and on the other hand, the fertility of subjectivity (Bardin, 1977). Allard-Poesi et al., (2007), note that: « *Although all of its potential is still little used in management research, content analysis has several advantages for the researcher. It is a methodology that can be used for both quantitative and qualitative research. It is applicable to a wide variety of types of documents or speeches and can focus on different levels of analysis (individual, group, department, organization or sector of activity* » (pp. 516-517).

For all these reasons, we consider that this method will allow us to determine the purpose of the publications, and thus answer our question on the uses made of the facebook pages by the Moroccan politicians. The results of the content analysis of publications of Moroccan politicians belonging to our sample are presented in the next section.

4. Data analysis and findings

The data collected through the screenshots of politicians' publications on their *Facebook* pages were processed manually, but also via soft data using Excel software. The first step is to qualify each publication according to the analysis grid previously established. Five categories of uses are distinguished according to the literature review: *Information, interaction, mobilization, fundraising and poll*. In the literature on political uses, the dissemination of information is associated with the exercise of transmitting information to a wide audience without waiting for feedback (Lilleker 2006). Williams et al., (1988), define interactivity as: « *the degree to which participants in the communication process have control over and can exchange roles in their mutual discourse* » (p.10). Mobilization refers to « *the process by which*

A MARKETING APPROACH OF MOROCCAN POLITICIANS' USES ON SOCIAL NETWORKS SITES

candidates, parties, activists, and groups induce other people to participate » in politics « to win elections, to pass bills, to modify rulings, [and] to influence policies » (Rosenstone and Hansen, 1993, p.25; p.30). According to Cambridge Dictionary, fundraising is the act of collecting or producing money for a particular purpose. In our case the purpose is fund a political campaign by soliciting subscribers' donations. Finally, poll is defined as a sampling or collection of opinions on a subject, taken from either a selected or a random group of persons, as for the purpose of analysis.

However, in processing the collected data, we noticed that some posts are devoted to expressing a point of view of the politician. This is why we have added to the analysis grid a sixth category of uses called "Stance". We rank a post in the category "Stance" when the politician post is intended to make known one's position, comment, reaction, thought or opinion about an issue or decision of public order. Moreover, fundraising category was eliminated from our analysis grid because, unlike the USA for example, the use of SNS to raise and collect funds is prohibited by law in Morocco. Table 2 presents the distribution of posts on the pages of Moroccan politicians who were part of our study sample.

Table 2: Distribution of posts on politician Facebook pages

Politicians	Position	Gender	subscribers	Information posts	Interaction Posts	Mobilization Posts	Stance posts	Poll Posts
P1	I	M	183,587	8	0	1	1	0
P2	I	M	9,559	6	0	0	4	0
P3	C	M	30,940	5	0	1	4	0
P4	I	M	124,934	8	0	2	0	0
P5	I	F	26,572	6	0	3	1	0
P6	I	M	76,500	9	0	0	1	0
P7	I	M	254,601	6	0	1	3	0
P8	C	M	306,980	9	0	0	1	0
P9	I	M	69,247	9	0	0	1	0
P10	I	M	14,325	9	0	0	1	0
P11	C	F	174,413	4	0	4	2	0
P12	C	M	160,666	4	3	1	2	0
P13	I	M	37,311	10	0	0	0	0
P14	I	M	78,714	9	0	0	1	0
P15	C	F	13,439	3	3	0	1	3
P16	C	M	29,768	3	1	4	2	0
Total				118	7	17	25	3

C: Challenger; I: Incumbent; M: Male; F: Female; The number of subscribers was extracted during July 2018.

A MARKETING APPROACH OF MOROCCAN POLITICIANS' USES ON SOCIAL NETWORKS SITES

The results indicate clearly that the most common use of *Facebook* pages by Moroccan politicians is information sharing and expression of stance. Indeed, 74% of the publications analyzed are intended to make information available to the subscribers of the page and 16% of posts are devoted to express an attitude which makes for these two types of use a total of 90%. The information shared relates in the case of incumbents to the activities carried out in the government or which are being carried out (reception, inauguration, meeting, speech, interview, press release, statements, proposals, participation, commitments, laws voted, ...), but also to the planned events. As for the challengers, the information relates mainly to the activities carried out in parliament (questions asked, proposed laws, committee meetings...) and to the positions taken on topical issues, opinions, TV shows, press interviews, organized events....

Unlike politicians in developed countries, it seems that Moroccan politicians do not share personal information with the subscribers of their pages. Indeed, we have not identified in the various publications indications about their private life, family life, hobbies or social activities. They limit themselves to sharing what relates to their political exercise. We are therefore still far from the phenomenon of the "personalization of politics" that characterizes the media practices of politicians in certain developed countries, especially the USA.

If the basic principle of digital social networks is to facilitate conversation, horizontal exchange and interaction between users, it is clear that Moroccan politicians, through their broadcast publications, are more likely to be part of a one-way and vertical communication. Their communication practices on SNS can be likened to an adaption of traditional media into a new context (Pettersson and Karlström, 2011). In their informational posts, Moroccan politicians often accompany text with photos and images to convey their messages. Some posts contain only a link to videos recorded during events and activities carried out by the politician. A few politicians make use of video to share regularly with subscribers their official activities. Only one politician shares in these videos with subscribers his tastes in music and reading. Other politicians prefer to share on their pages only photos with hashtags or links to other sites which can redirect subscribers to more content.

It should be noted that the proportion of posts devoted to information is higher among incumbents (80%) than among challengers (47%). Because they are in government,

A MARKETING APPROACH OF MOROCCAN POLITICIANS' USES ON SOCIAL NETWORKS SITES

incumbents tend to talk more about their achievements to show citizens that they have kept their promises. They are somehow in a “*defense political marketing*”.

The other uses, namely interaction and mobilization, represent only a small proportion: (4%) % and (11%) respectively for incumbents and challengers. It is also apparent from the study that challengers, rather young, who use the most *Facebook* to interact, react to comments and mobilize the subscribers of their pages. Several of their publications were intended to publish calls to subscribers of their pages to attend meetings and events or to sign a petition. Challengers react the most to some subscribers' comments and even answer their questions. While incumbents sometimes devote posts to react to what they consider as rumors by making corrections or clarifications. Although the platform allows it, we noticed that incumbents avoid reacting to the comments of subscribers in an individualized way. It therefore appears that Moroccan politicians who are incumbents are still reluctant to sign up for an exchange and interaction with subscribers of their pages, whereas challengers use *facebook* mainly as vector of information and mobilization.

In the same sense, the findings also indicate that Moroccan politicians, whether incumbents or challengers, rarely take the initiative to discuss with subscribers about issues of concern to the public. A single post from a challenger politician was intended to ask for proposals and ideas from subscribers. We have also not identified any post in which Moroccan politicians probe subscribers' opinions by asking them questions with possible answer options. Online survey platforms such as “*Survey Monkey*” or “*Google Docs*” could help politicians design and conduct surveys on their *Facebook* pages and even spread it on other pages. Without going far, *Facebook* even offers a feature and its own application to do easily surveys with images, GIF and videos.

To finish the uses made of *Facebook* pages by Moroccan politicians, no post was dedicated to asking donations that they be material or financial or at least to ask for volunteers among the subscribers. The last section of this article is devoted to the discussion of these results as well as to conclusions.

5. Discussion and conclusion

The content analysis of 160 posts of a sample of the most 16 active Moroccan politicians on *Facebook* revealed that the pages are mainly used to broadcast official information about their activities. *Facebook* is used primarily as a dissemination mechanism. The interactive features offered by these digital platforms are not yet exploited by Moroccan politicians, because they are more focused on communicating their positions. This posture could, in our opinion, allow the politician to avoid communication slippages or lose control of the image he seeks to convey to its targets on the SNS. The recurrence of posts of vertical diffusion of the information corresponds in the evolution of political marketing, to a "*product orientation*" (Lees-Marshment, 2003). The other uses, namely mobilizing and engaging subscribers through social networks sites, respectively sales and market orientation phases, are still weak in the digital practices of Moroccan politicians. Building on the distinction made by Less-Marshment, (2003), Williams and Gulati, (2015), clearly explain the difference between these three phases in the following passage:

« Product orientation focuses on their platform and issue positions while a sales orientation is focused on using market research to develop and implement advertising and communication techniques to persuade voters. Market orientation, in contrast, uses intelligence not just to identify voters' needs and wants, but to respond to and meet them » (p.277).

In fact, these findings on the use of SNS by Moroccan politicians are similar to those found in other countries, but during the first years of web 2.0 penetration (e.g. Lilleker, 2009; Small, 2010). What it shows may be that adherence to the characteristics of web 2.0 takes time. This time is necessary for politicians to adopt and appropriate the functionalities allowed by these new technologies of communication and mobilization. Certainly, the use of SNS for political marketing purposes is a new phenomenon in Morocco. Moroccan politicians are just beginning to accept and adopt these new tools and discover their potential, but there are several other factors that we believe are driving these results.

A successful and effective presence on the SNS first requires knowledge and skills in digital political marketing. In developed countries, politicians use advisory services in this area. They are often communication and consulting companies who have gained experience in the

A MARKETING APPROACH OF MOROCCAN POLITICIANS' USES ON SOCIAL NETWORKS SITES

commercial field and are trying to adapt this expertise to the political field. In Morocco, such companies are still rare. Moreover, the weakness of the interactive uses of SNS by Moroccan politicians could be explained, in our opinion, by the fact that it also requires a watch and a permanent presence to react quickly to comments, especially those that are negative. It is clear that the politician alone can not do it. The support of a whole team of assistants and advisers is essential. These investments probably require substantial financial resources for the digital communication component of the politician's communication plan. On the technical side, the difficulty of mastering the published contents and the reactions of the subscribers makes that Moroccan politicians are limited to the vertical diffusion of the information. Therefore, we can say that they are in the same logic as in the traditional media. Nevertheless, beyond the question of financial and human resources, it seems that Moroccan politicians are mostly unaware of the potential that SNS offer in terms of political marketing. Thus, regarding the lack of use of SNS by Moroccan politicians to conduct opinion polls, we believe that this is related to the perception that Moroccan politicians have of political marketing in general. Indeed, this one is often perceived, according to several studies, as a tool of communication and not yet a tool of knowledge and understanding of the electorate. We are so far from the process of political marketing as developed by the pioneers of the discipline (Kotler and Levy, 1969; Kotler, 1972, 1975; Hunt, 1976), and which the study phase is the cornerstone of any successful marketing decision.

Regarding the difference of SNS use between the challengers and incumbents, we consider that it depends on the objectives of each one. Their uses overall seem similar and each one uses in its own way the tools offered on the SNS to achieve its goals. However, the introduction of the concept of "*permanent campaign*" into political marketing research (e.g., Sparrow and Turner, 2001, Butler and Collins, 1994) is likely to further reduce differences in the use of SNS between both actors. Indeed, in the "*permanent campaign*", the campaign process and the government process have lost their distinctiveness (Ornstein and Mann, 2000). All politicians are in a perpetual state of relationship marketing (Pettersson and Karlström, 2011).

Despite all the constraints to the full use of SNS by Moroccan politicians that we quoted above, we can say that digital practices will change over time. A new generation of politicians is beginning to emerge. Our study has shown that young politicians in our sample are most likely

A MARKETING APPROACH OF MOROCCAN POLITICIANS' USES ON SOCIAL NETWORKS SITES

to adhere to the interactive features of SNS. This trend in the use of SNS could challenge many findings in the literature which argue that politicians primarily use SNS for the purpose of disseminating information.

In the end, this study certainly provides insights into the uses made of social networks by Moroccan politicians, but obviously does not escape certain limits. First, we have limited ourselves in the observation of the SNS to the uses made of *Facebook*, knowing that Moroccan politicians also use *Twitter* and to a lesser extent *Youtube*. Secondly, we only observed pages, while Moroccan politicians also use groups and personal accounts on *Facebook*. Thirdly, the observation period did not coincide with any election period when the uses made of the SNS could be more intense, but also more diversified. Future studies that take into account these three limits could, in our view, lead to more precise results.

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